

Audio file

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Transcript

Speaker 1

Hello, my name is Anna Makarudze and I am pursuing a Masters in Software Engineering at the Institute of Technology and I'm conducting research for my thesis investigating how developers in the data receive vulnerabilities in FOSS and OSS students they include in their project. And participation in this research is entirely voluntary, and you can withdraw from the interview at any time. We will not retain any personal data or identifiable information, and we will not share your personal details or publish them. And you can skip any questions that you're not comfortable answering, and your responses will remain anonymous. And then the interview will be recorded and kept for the duration of the study to allow the supervisors and examiners to verify the authenticity of the reported data, after which it will be deleted and will comply with all GDPR regulations.

So before we start, maybe you can start by introducing yourself and the projects for which you are a developer or a contributor or maintainer. your job title, how many years of experience you have with the framework that you are using, or how long you've been a software developer. So I'm focusing on developers from Django, Spring Boot that I've built, Ruby on Rails, as well as Next.js So you can tell me which framework you're using for your projects. it's part of your introduction. Okay.

Speaker 2

Thank you. Thank you, Anna, for the introduction.

And my name is, and I'm a full stack developer. So I've been in software engineering for like for the first like six years. So I'm currently working remotely in a company called So I'm working remotely. The company is based in UK. So I'm working in both like front end and back end. So the company we are into like SaaS products. So we have several SaaS application and we have a reasonable client base. So one of our application is like our event manager, which is popular. So the event manager application, we use it to like manage event, book event, and also like manage a lot of public events like from our application. So one of the technologies we are using is we are using Laravel. So Laravel as

the back end for some of the microservices. So we are using it to sub multiple back end services. And also in some other application we are using like Python, Django. But we usually focus on-- I usually work on the Laravel, but I also get involved in the Django and other projects. Yeah, I think that's basically it. I don't know if I missed something.

Speaker 1

Yeah. All right. And what's your role in the project? Are you back in software front end?

Speaker 2

Yeah, I'm a full stack. I'm a full stack engineer. So I usually work both front end and back end. Yeah.

Speaker 1

All right. Thank you. OK. My next question is, how are security issues report punished within your project?

Speaker 2

OK. Yeah, yeah. So in terms of security, right? Most of the times we are usually conscious about security and we usually pay attention to some of the packages we usually install on our application. And in some cases, in some cases, not all the time, in some cases we usually like check, we, or I would say we depend on GitHub, you know, notifications.

In most cases, when you're using a package and it's kind of a part of your repo, so one day it's like a security concern or maybe a vulnerability, GitHub usually raise a plug and we usually like update work on that and update the application.

So I think that's our major approach when it comes to like security. So we don't have like any like a technical maybe a team dedicated to like security and all that stuff. So usually like depend on that for our packages that we use in our repo.

Speaker 1

Yeah. Alright. And, how conscious are you of the dangers that vulnerable dependages present to your projects?

Speaker 2

Yeah, yeah, so I'm aware of, like, the most common vulnerabilities on projects. So for example, I'm aware of like SQL injection. And maybe let's say you call a scripting and some of the basic like the common vulnerabilities. So am aware of both of them. So in most cases, so I we try to like avoid having issues like that.

Speaker 1

All right. And how are you of supply chain attacks in their effects on projects?

Speaker 2

Supply chain attacks. I haven't heard about that one. So I haven't heard about that one. So I'm not aware about something like that. So this is my first time like hearing about supply chain attack.

Speaker 1

All right. And how do you identify dependencies with vulnerabilities within your project?

Speaker 2

Yeah, so usually like I mentioned, usually we depend on like GitHub. GitHub a repository. GitHub repos usually, I think they usually scan and send a notification when there is like a vulnerability on most of the package, on any package in your repo.

So anytime there is like something a security flow or something like that, so I think in most cases, GitHub usually send an update, usually send notification that this package is compromised, you have to update to some version or something like that.

Speaker 1

All right. And what influences the decision to update to newer versions of the dependencies within your project?

Speaker 2

Can you come again, please? Sorry, I didn't hear.

Speaker 1

I'm saying what influences the decision to update to newer versions of the dependencies within your project? Do you update just because there's a newer version or do you update because you have received maybe a notification from GitHub Dependabot.

Speaker 2

So, okay, so we normally, so normally if something is in production, if something is in production and it's working, usually updates stop most of the time. So we, in most cases, update usually come when there is a need for that update or when there is a vulnerability.

So for example, let's say GitHub send us an e-mail, there's a vulnerability. And when we look at the risk, so that vulnerability has a high risk. So then we usually like focus on that

and update that. But apart from that, we don't usually update like any time. We just, we just, as long as something is running, so we don't touch it.

Speaker 1

Yeah. Okay. And you mentioned you use, you mostly use Laravel. But do you use dependencies, when you are working on Laravel projects, do you use maybe dependencies from other ecosystems such as maybe JavaScript libraries or do you only use like within the PHP ecosystem?

Speaker 2

Yeah, so most of the, let's say for example, Laravel, since most of our applications, most of the, most of our Laravel applications are usually APIs. So they're usually by APIs. So and most of our most of our dependency libraries are usually just strictly php libraries. So we just use our composer to to manage most of them.

Speaker 1

Thank you. And how do you handle vulnerable dependencies within your project?

Speaker 2

So in most cases, right? We just update, let's say, like, if it is a package, we just update the package to a newer version to avoid that one. So, most cases, we just update it. So, and let's say, for, close, let's say, since since we don't usually carry out, like, we don't usually carry out, like, maybe security penetration testing or something like that. So, in most cases, we don't, we don't usually even... experience like this plus or we don't really have these issues. So only for dependencies. So does in most cases we only work on dependencies and for dependencies is just update. We just update. That's all.

Speaker 1

All right. And in the event that maybe the dependent is no longer being maintained and there is no newer version to update to, how do we handle that?

Speaker 2

Yeah. So in that case, in that case, so in that case, most of the time, we just, we just like, I think most of them are ignored, so most of them are ignored, so most of them are ignored, most of them are ignored, so except maybe... I think something is critical, very critical issue. But in that case, most of them are just ignored. We just ignore it. Yeah, we just ignore them. Yeah, I'm just like, yeah.

Speaker 1

And how do you check the maintenance of the dependence in your project? Because usually with open source projects, creators tend to abandon only their projects and become unmaintained. So do you check to see whether the dependency you are using are still being maintained or just leave it as long as everything is working, you get when it's normal.

Speaker 2

Yeah. So most of the time we don't like when it comes to like just dependencies, most of the time we don't actually like check especially like go and check. So because like even, you know, developers usually are usually always like building something, working on new features. So it's not, we don't have like the, we don't spend time usually like going through dependencies and checking update and looking, but we don't usually do that.

So I think, if I remember, so it's well, in most cases, let's say for a node, let's say notification, if you are dealing with JS, so you know when you are using NPM or YARN, so it's usually like through some, something like that, usually through like update notification or something like that.

So, but apart from that, I don't think, especially in PHP, Laravel, I don't think we, we don't follow up with that. So only like, we only depend on that GitHub that I mentioned earlier.

So.

Speaker 1

And, okay, so how long does it take to update vulnerable dependencies within your project?

Speaker 2

Yeah, it's quite, it's quite easy. It's quite easy. Like, we're going to update. It's quite easy. So it's maybe our application kind of break. If our application break, do an update, then we'll see. So we have to like check and see what is not compatible and which library maybe is dependent on this. And now we'll take maybe a time, maybe let's say hours or maybe some will take days. So I can remember working on one library whereby.

I want dependency whereby a lot of dependencies are dependent on that, and the thing is like the new version is not compatible with other versions, and when we update, if you update that dependency, we have to update the other ones, and the other hands also have complications on our application on desktop, so that one like kind of took me like maybe a week, I think that time I have to like work on a tweak, I have to work on...

I have to manually do some changes on the dependency to kind of tweak it to just work with the with the with the old ones, something like that. It took me almost a week for that one. But in most cases it's like easy, just like ours, which will get updated.

00:13:15 Speaker 1

Okay, so I mostly use Django. And what what is common in Django is if

Dependent is no longer being maintained and people rely on that other community members usually step up to take over that dependence. For example, just being maintaining many projects and even though it's sunsetting now, Django Commons now taking over that role. So I'm wondering, is it common for in the PHP community for other maintainers to step up to take over abandoned projects because they are being able to use or once the owner or the creator of that project moves away, then and then it stays on that project.

Speaker 2

I think in like a PHP community, right, especially Larabelle, I haven't experienced something like that. I haven't experienced something like that because in most time in PHP there are a lot of dead libraries, like there are a lot of dead dependencies, libraries are most of them.

So I've never experienced like any like library teaching, any community takeover and some of the like dependency libraries and most of the time in PHP I haven't experienced that. So most of the time it's just like, it's just most of them are just like some of them, a lot of them are not even popular, like maybe JavaScript and other stuff. So in PHP only few are kind of like that are popular when it come to like dependencies. Yeah.

Speaker 1

And you mentioned dead dependencies and suppose you are using a dead dependency. What do you keep on using it or do you move to something? Yes, most of the time.

Speaker 2

Yeah, most of the time as long as the dependency is giving me what I want. So I just, we just, yeah, we just keep using it.

Speaker 1

Yeah. And what factors help you to address vulnerable dependencies within your project?

Speaker 2

Can you-- can I call again? I didn't get you.

Speaker 1

OK. I'm saying, what pictures help you to make a decision to address vulnerable dependencies within your project.

Speaker 2

OK, OK, OK.

We only have, I would say we only have one method, right? The only method is to look at the risk. So it's to look at the risk and compare it with how, and to just compare it with the, with the effect and hot base, right? So maybe it's a high risk. Sometimes, you know, it's just like, it's just a, maybe what I say, just like a medium rate or maybe a low risk or something like that.

So for those ones, if like a upgrade or update is for medium ones, as long as the update is not, if the update is hard, let's say if it's update, if the update is updating, it will cause issues and other stuff and it's hard.

So we usually ignore a medium to low risk like this thing. So but to low risk vulnerabilities. But for let's say high risk. We usually try our best like to see we we we updated or we patched the vulnerability in most cases.

But our only decision is based on like and our only method is just to to see if how it will affect us and how rigs are and level of rigs is kind of it kind of exposed to our application. So we don't have like any standard like go with yeah.

Speaker 1

And what challenges do you face which hinder you in addressing vulnerable dependencies within your project?

Speaker 2

Okay, so I think one of the biggest challenges is, let's say, compatibility with other dependencies. So like an area, so if a package like, let's say the vulnerability, the package that has vulnerability has dependency with other, maybe the object is going to cause like dependency issue with other dependency dependency component or libraries.

So so that's one of the major issue. So you know, yeah, if you update this a lot of things are going to break. So and now it depends. Some will take, like I mentioned, some will take like months or maybe weeks to fix, because sometimes you even it has to. It has to come to a stage whereby you have to even maybe work on it maybe manually.

So you don't, you don't have to, we are not going to depend on the, you're not going to depend on the patch. So you just have to maybe try and fix it manually from yourself, maybe and tweak it, maybe hack it to just work with your current system. Yeah.

Speaker 1

And what recommendations do you have for dependency management? Mitigate, yeah. Or any other security risks, yeah.

Speaker 2

Okay, okay, yeah, yeah, yeah, I think, I think for now, I don't know, I don't know if like maybe there is now, I don't know if there is maybe any integration, let's say in our IDE, maybe in IDEs, maybe if there is maybe a module or a module that you can install and it will keep like, it will be like giving you update whereby like this dependency has issue and this is how to patch it or this is how to work on it.

So I don't know if there is something like that exists, but I believe if there's something like that, is going to also that is going to help. So, and it's going to be like, it's going to be like a beta version of the NPM, you know, the NPM one that we have currently.

So a module, I think it will be much better, maybe integrated to our IDE. So if you install it, only time it will be giving you like heads up, like this is what's... happening. So I think that would be like my suggestion.

Speaker 1

Thank you so much. I think that's all. Thank you so much for taking your time to participate in this interview.

Speaker 2

Okay, thank you. Thank you. Thank you, Anna, for having me.

Speaker 2

So actually, your questions kind of open a lot of questions for me also from my side. It's kind of, it's going to like also help me, help us like become more cautious now because there are actually some things that I've never think about because like in most cases we are just busy like developing and building stuff. So we don't even, we don't usually question some things like that. Yeah, thank you. Thank you for having me.

Speaker 1

Thank you so much.

